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AN INVESTIGATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JUNIOR CYCLE SCIENCE STUDENTS' SPATIAL ABILITY AND SCIENTIFIC REASONING

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ABSTRACT

Research has shown that spatial ability is important for success in STEM. Spatial ability is closely linked with understanding often complex scientific concepts. It is important that the future STEM workforce, the current students in second level education, are developing their spatial ability and hence strengthening their STEM skills. This study presents an investigation of the relationship between spatial ability and scientific reasoning within Junior Cycle (1st-3rd year of second level) science students (12-15 years old). The tests used in this study are the Mental Rotation Test (MRT) [1] and the Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning (CTSR) [2]. This study is part of a larger study currently in progress. Due to the current health crisis, the entire study could not be completed at this time. Data has been gathered for 84 students to date, with further testing scheduled for 100-200 students once restrictions are lifted. This paper presents preliminary findings to date. The analysis shows a significant correlation between Junior Cycle science students' spatial ability and scientific reasoning. There was no significant gender differences observed, however the percentage increase in spatial ability and scientific reasoning from first year to third year was higher for the boys. This study is relevant, as a better understanding of how to educate low spatial ability students, a group over-represented by females, in second level education could lead to the development of strong STEM skills and ultimately a higher uptake of the study of STEM by female students at second and third level.

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1 INTRODUCTION

There is a large gender imbalance within STEM disciplines and careers in Ireland today. In a report by Kavanagh et al [3], they estimated that only 25% of the STEM workforce is made up of women. There have been many research studies aimed at explaining and addressing this often observed gender gap within STEM fields [4-7]. It is a complex issue, where girls choose to not pursue their studies in STEM for many reasons. In order to be successful in effecting change, a multi-faceted approach would be ideal [3, 8]. Parents and teachers are one of the largest influences when it comes to girls choosing their subjects in school and third level education pursuits in Ireland [8].

However, there are also cognitive barriers to consider. Spatial ability has been strongly linked with success in STEM [4, 5, 9]. The link between scientific reasoning and spatial ability has been highlighted in various studies [10-12]. A particularly important finding from spatial ability research is the large and repeatable gender differences favouring males [6]. The largest gender differences are generally observed in tests of mental rotation, the particular spatial skill most associated with success in STEM [4, 13]. In this study, the aim is to investigate the levels of spatial ability, specifically, mental rotation ability, and scientific reasoning of a sample of Junior Cycle science students. If the relationship between these variables is better understood in this context, then this could lead to improvements in teaching practice, and help to aid the female students in particular to develop strong scientific and problem solving skills at this important time in their STEM learning. The research questions are:

- What is the relationship between Junior Cycle science students' skills in spatial ability and scientific reasoning?
- What are the gender differences, if any, of the Junior Cycle science students' spatial ability and scientific reasoning?

2 METHODOLOGY

For this study, Junior Cycle science students in one mixed school in Ireland were administered the MRT and CTSR tests within their normal science class (40 minutes duration). The MRT was given first, taking 7 minutes, and the CTSR given second, taking 30 minutes. 84 students were tested, with 32 students in first year, 18 students in second year, and 34 students in third year. 55 students were male, and 29 students were female. The age range was between 12-15 years old. All the students were taking the same level science class in Junior Cycle. All students had the opportunity to read and sign an informed consent form for the study. The researcher administered the tests in class, adhering to the recommended protocol and time limit for each subsequent test. The tests were presented as reasoning and problem solving tasks. The students were encouraged to answer each question honestly.

2.1 Instruments

For this study, two psychometric tests were employed. The Mental Rotation Test (MRT) [1] was chosen to measure spatial ability. This test is the redrawn Vandenburg & Kuse [14] mental rotation test. The MRT is a test of mental rotation ability specifically, a factor of spatial ability that has been shown to have large and repeatable gender differences [4, 6, 7, 13]. The MRT has 24 questions, with each question having four possible answers to choose from. For each question, two answers are correct, therefore 1 point is awarded only if the two options selected are both correct. The Junior Cycle science students' age is comparable to the US middle school student population (11-14 years old). The MRT has been shown to be suitable to use with this age group of students [15, 16]. In terms of test validity, Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.87 [17].

For the scientific reasoning measure, the Lawson Classroom Test of Scientific Reasoning (CTSR) [2] has been chosen. The test aligns well with the learning outcomes of the Junior Cycle science curriculum, and is suitable for middle school age students. The CTSR has 24 questions, with each question having between three to five possible answers to choose from, with one correct answer per question. Questions 1-22 are paired, therefore one point is awarded only if both parts are answered correctly, i.e. questions 1 & 2, questions 3 & 4, and so on. Questions 23 and 24 are stand alone questions, with one correct answer per question. In terms of test validity, Cronbach's reliability was found to be 0.70 [18].

3 RESULTS

For this study, the variables were examined to investigate if gender differences existed for mental rotation ability and scientific reasoning. Table 1 shows the mean values in percentages of the variables, separated by gender.

Table 1: Comparisons of means for the MRT and CTSR by gender.

Test	Male			Female			t-test	Sig (2-tailed)
	n	Mean (%)	SD	n	Mean (%)	SD		
MRT	55	33.12	23.20	29	27.87	20.36	1.024	.309
CTSR	55	32.86	16.70	29	32.65	15.19	.064	.949

Table 1 shows the mean scores in percentage correct, averaged over all three years. An independent sample t-test was then performed, which showed there were no significant differences by gender for either measure. The sample is small and mixed in age range, therefore significant conclusions cannot be drawn at this stage of the study. Table 2 below shows the mean values of the variables, separated by year and gender.

Table 2: Comparisons of means for the MRT and CTSR by gender and year.

Test	Year	Mean Age	n	Male		Female		
				Mean (%)	SD	n	Mean (%)	SD
MRT	1	13	21	25.78	18.40	11	22.36	13.61
CTSR	1	13	21	27.86	17.23	11	30.79	14.18
MRT	2	14	12	33.34	27.52	6	45.13	33.89
CTSR	2	14	12	26.95	13.73	6	34.63	18.03
MRT	3	15	22	39.96	23.30	12	24.30	12.53
CTSR	3	15	22	40.92	14.86	12	33.36	15.84

Again, as the sample numbers are very small, no significant conclusions can be drawn. However, it is interesting to note that when the percentage increase in spatial ability and scientific reasoning is calculated from first year to third year, the boys percentage increase in spatial ability was 55.0%, compared to the girls at 8.7%. Similarly for scientific reasoning, the boys percentage increase was 46.9%, compared to the girls at 8.3%. Although the n is very small, this is an interesting preliminary finding. If this proves to hold as the sample increases, this could potentially indicate that, although the girls appear to have a similar level of skills as the boys in first year, they are not developing their spatial ability and scientific understanding as much as the boys do, as they progress through their science education. As this experience of Junior Cycle science is the basis for the students' subsequent choices of what subjects to pursue at leaving certificate level, this could mean that the girls are at a disadvantage when choosing to pursue STEM subjects further, and are perhaps more likely to avoid them. This is only speculative at this stage. Table 3 below, shows the correlational relationship between the variables.

Table 3: Correlation for MRT and CTSR

	n	CTSR	Sig. (2-tailed)
MRT	84	.502**	.000

The results show a moderate positive statistically significant correlation at the .01 percentile between mental rotation ability, and scientific reasoning. These preliminary findings suggest that there is a relationship between second level science students' spatial ability, and understanding of scientific concepts.

4 SUMMARY

The findings from this preliminary study showed no significant gender differences for spatial ability or scientific reasoning. However, the percentage increase from first year to third year in spatial ability and scientific reasoning was higher for boys, at 55.0% and 46.9% respectively, compared to the girls, at 8.7% and 8.3%. The correlational analysis showed a moderate positive relationship between spatial ability and scientific reasoning for Junior Cycle science students. This possibly indicates that a student's strength in reasoning spatially is related to their understanding of scientific concepts. However, as the sample is so small, no significant conclusions can be drawn from this study. As this paper is a work in progress, it will be interesting to analyse the data within the context of a larger sample as the study progresses.

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